

RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF GRP AT HIGH CYCLE FATIGUE

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SUMMARY: Residual strength degradation of glass-fiber reinforced polyester composite of a lay-up typical for wind rotor blade material is studied at low-cycle fatigue. Gradual reduction of remaining strength is observed as expected for GRP, accompanied by increasing scatter. Residual strength model based on strength-life equal rank assumption yields accurate approximation of experimental data. Strength reduction at stress level corresponding to high-cycle fatigue ($N > 10^6$ cycles) appears to correlate well with higher stress level test results indicating that strength degradation at design stress level can be evaluated using low-cycle tests. Assuming that strength degradation model parameters do not depend on applied stress level, residual strength data obtained at low stress level tests of comparatively short duration can be used to estimate the average fatigue life at the same stress thus considerably reducing total test time.

KEYWORDS: fatigue, residual strength, glass/polyester composite

INTRODUCTION

Fail-safe strength design of engineering composite structures has to ensure that appropriate residual static strength level is maintained during design life. The latter is typically too long to allow conventional fatigue and residual strength tests to be performed at the desired low design stress level. Hence fatigue test data are usually extrapolated to low stress levels of interest. In order to improve the accuracy of remaining strength and life estimates, a model of composite fatigue behavior during high-cycle fatigue verified by experimental data is necessary.

Residual strength models have been developed for prediction of residual strength and life distribution under constant amplitude, block [1], and spectrum loading [2]. Modifications taking into account mean stress effect [3], competing failure modes [4], degradation mechanism change [5] have been proposed. In [6] residual strength model is used to extrapolate experimentally derived S-N curves. The model predictions satisfactorily agree with experimental data in the stress range covered, which in most investigations is limited by that corresponding to fatigue life of about 10^6 cycles. Less research is dedicated to strength degradation at lower cyclic stress levels which are of primary significance for long-term applications.

With this aim residual strength degradation at a range of stress levels has been studied experimentally, and a method of fatigue life estimation based on limited amount of residual strength tests at the stress level of interest is proposed.

MATERIAL AND TESTS

Glass fiber reinforced polyester used as a blade material for wind turbines was tested. The material was produced by hand lay-up, and comprised chopped strand mat, unidirectionally reinforced, and fabric layers in the following sequence: /CSM, fabric,(CSM, UD)₂/ s. The resin used was an orthophthalic polyester (Norpol 410M910). The average fiber volume fraction was 41 %. Longitudinal modulus and tensile strength were correspondingly $E = 30 \pm 2$ GPa and $S = 672 \pm 21$ MPa.

Dog-bone shape specimens were used for tensile static strength and fatigue tests. Static strength distribution is shown in Fig. 1, and fatigue diagram - in Fig. 2. Fatigue tests were run at ambient conditions. Loading frequency was 17 Hz, stress ratio $r = 0.1$. Residual tensile strength degradation was studied at a number of stress levels. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Residual strength

Maximum stress, MPa	Duration of loading, cycles	Duration of loading, fraction of nominal life*	Number of specimens tested	Average residual strength, MPa	Standard deviation of residual strength, MPa
284	$2.5 \cdot 10^4$.17	7	604	27
	$5 \cdot 10^4$.33	9	555	35
	$1 \cdot 10^5$.66	7	507	53
	$1.24 \cdot 10^5$.82	8	493	82
235	$2 \cdot 10^5$.15	6	628	27
	$4 \cdot 10^5$.30	7	598	30
221	$4 \cdot 10^5$.16	5	628	31
206	$4 \cdot 10^5$.08	5	634	28
186	$8 \cdot 10^5$.07	7	635	35
167	$1.6 \cdot 10^6$.06	5	617	3

*life fraction reported in the Table is calculated with respect to linear approximation of $\lg N$ vs. σ diagram

MODELING OF RESIDUAL STRENGTH DEGRADATION

Majority of residual strength R degradation models can be derived from the following rate equation:

$$\frac{dR}{dn} = f(\sigma, r, S)g(R)h(n) \quad (1)$$

supplemented by initial condition $R(0) = S$ and failure criterion $R(N) = \sigma$, where R - residual strength, S - static strength, N - fatigue life at cyclic stress with maximum value σ , n - current number of loading cycles. Non-linearity of strength reduction is accounted for by appropriate choice of functions g and h . Models derived assuming that strength degradation rate does not explicitly depend on either n (i.e. $h=1$) or R are commonly used. Since there is little physical background for favoring any of these approaches, both of them are considered below.

Statistical Model

Taking $g = \frac{1}{v} R^{-v+1}$, $h \equiv 1$ and $f = -\frac{S^v - \sigma^v}{S^c - \sigma^c} \frac{1}{N^*}$, residual strength model [7] is recovered,

and residual strength R of a specimen with initial static strength value S after fatigue loading of n cycles at a constant maximum stress level σ is:

$$R^v = S^v - \frac{S^v - \sigma^v}{S^c - \sigma^c} \frac{n}{N^*} \quad (2)$$

Residual strength distribution is derived in [7] assuming Weibull distribution function for static strength S :

$$F_S(S) = 1 - \exp[-S^\alpha] \quad (3)$$

and fatigue life (at constant maximum stress level σ):

$$F_N(n) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\sigma^c + \frac{n}{N^*}\right)^{\alpha/c}\right] \quad (4)$$

All variables with stress dimension are normalized by Weibull scale parameter β of static strength distribution; N^* - characteristic fatigue life at stress level σ . It follows from (4) that it is related to the mean life \bar{N} :

$$\bar{N} = N^* \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{c}{\alpha}\right) + \sigma^c \quad (5)$$

Residual strength distribution is given by Eqn 6:

$$F_R(R) = 1 - \exp[S_0^\alpha - S(R)^\alpha] \quad (6)$$

where by $S(R)$ is denoted the static strength value corresponding to residual strength R and obtained solving (2) for S . Parameter S_0 accounts for the fact that residual strength can be determined only for the specimens that have survived fatigue loading, i.e. for which $R(n) > \sigma$. Therefore S_0 is calculated from (2) replacing R by σ .

The model described comprises five material parameters. They were estimated by maximum likelihood method as corresponding distribution function parameters in the following order. First, strength distribution scale and shape parameters β and α were evaluated fitting (3) to static strength test results (see Fig. 1), then parameter c characterizing fatigue life scatter and characteristic S-N curve $\lg N^* = A - B\sigma$ parameters A and B were determined approximating constant amplitude fatigue data (Fig. 2) by (4), and the remaining residual strength degradation rate parameter ν - fitting (6) to residual strength data at $\sigma = 284$ MPa (Fig. 3). Parameter values are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Model parameter values

α	β , MPa	c	A	B , MPa ⁻¹	ν
35.1	683	10.8	10.7	.019	2.45

Deterministic Model

If $h(n) = \gamma \cdot n^{\gamma-1}$ and $g(R) \equiv 1$ are taken in Eqn 1, it follows that residual strength degrades under constant amplitude cyclic loading according to relation (7):

$$R = S - (S - \sigma) \left(\frac{n}{N} \right)^\gamma \quad (7)$$

Although the model allows statistical treatment, strength and fatigue life in Eqn 7 are normally substituted by their average values therefore making model deterministic (see e.g. [8]).

Deterministic model, unlike the statistical one, cannot account for apparent slowing down of strength reduction at n approaching mean fatigue life N (and caused by failure of weaker specimens during cycling). Therefore average residual strength values at $\sigma = 284$ MPa obtained at loading duration up to $.66N$ only were used for parameter γ determination, resulting in $\gamma = 1.33$ (see Fig. 4).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Residual strength data apparently form a mastercurve (Fig. 5), when plotted as a function of nominal life fraction spent under cyclic load. It makes it possible to roughly estimate residual strength reduction at low cyclic stress level using high stress level data. Variation of remaining strength for small to medium loading duration in terms of life fraction ($n/N < .35$) is very close to that of static strength with the exception of the lowest stress level considered $\sigma = 167$ MPa. Standard deviation of residual strength for the latter was almost an order of magnitude less than that of static strength.

In order to check whether strength degradation model parameters are stress dependent, they were determined from two residual strength data sets obtained at $\sigma = 284$ MPa (corresponding fatigue life $N = 1.9 \cdot 10^5$) and $\sigma = 235$ MPa ($N = 1.7 \cdot 10^6$). Stress levels were chosen so that they lay within the stress range at which fatigue tests were performed, so that reliable estimate of

corresponding fatigue lives was available. Model parameters for data generated at $\sigma = 284$ MPa are listed above, while for $\sigma = 235$ MPa they are $\nu = 2.36$ (statistical model) and $\gamma = 1.28$ (deterministic model). The difference in parameter values determined at different stress levels is negligible for both models, therefore they can be considered material parameters. Prediction of residual strength distribution at $\sigma = 235$ MPa by statistical model (Fig. 6, 7) and mean strength degradation by deterministic model (Fig. 4) using model parameters determined at $\sigma = 284$ MPa show very good agreement with test data.

Assuming that further reduction of cyclic stress level will not influence model parameters, low stress residual strength data can be used for estimation of the corresponding fatigue life. For deterministic model, relation for mean life estimate at stress σ follows from Eqn 7:

$$N = n \left(\frac{S - \sigma}{S - R} \right)^{1/\gamma} \quad (8)$$

For statistical model, maximum likelihood method was used for determining the value of N^* in Eqn 2 that yields the best fit of distribution function (6) to residual strength data obtained at the corresponding maximum cyclic stress σ . Theoretical residual strength distributions are plotted in Fig. 8-10. This method allows to calculate also standard deviation of N , thus allowing to evaluate the accuracy of prediction. For the lowest cyclic stress value considered estimated variation of N was of the same order as N clearly indicating that statistical model is not applicable in this case.

Predicted fatigue life at low stress is shown in Fig. 2. Fatigue life estimates by both residual strength models are very close to each other, and slightly below extrapolation line of experimental S-N data.

CONCLUSIONS

Residual strength data vs. life fraction of GRP under load form a mastercurve, from which a rough estimate of strength reduction at the cyclic stress level of interest can be obtained.

Strength degradation model parameters appear not to depend on cyclic stress level. It permits to estimate fatigue life of composite at a given stress level from a limited amount of residual strength test results at the same test level.

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Fig. 1: Static tensile strength distribution of GRP

Fig. 2: Fatigue diagram
 (x) - S-N data; mean life predicted by statistical (□) and deterministic (■) models

Fig. 3: Residual strength reduction at $\sigma = 284 \text{ MPa}$
 Statistical residual strength model prediction for failure probabilities .5 (—) ;
 .1 and .9 (- - -)

Fig. 4: Mean strength degradation at $\sigma = 284$ MPa (■) and $\sigma = 235$ MPa (○)
Lines -deterministic model prediction

Fig. 5: Residual strength vs. nominal life fraction for different cyclic stress levels

Fig. 6: Residual strength distribution after 200000 cycles at $\sigma = 235$ MPa

Fig. 7: Residual strength distribution after 400000 cycles at $\sigma = 235$ MPa

Fig. 8: Residual strength distribution after 400000 cycles at $\sigma = 221$ MPa

Fig. 9: Residual strength distribution after 400000 cycles at $\sigma = 206$ MPa

Fig. 10: Residual strength distribution after 800000 cycles at $\sigma = 186$ MPa